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A stupid plagiarism in the article « Ethnopharmacology and phytochemical screening of bioactive extracts of *Limoniastrum feei* (plombagenaceae) » Asian Journal of Natural & Applied Sciences, Vol. 2(1), 5-9, 2013

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EDITORIAL

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It's well known that plagiarism is considered misconduct research, unethical, perturb and damage the integrity and knowledge of the scientific community. In addition that is a form of violation copyright law and is therefore illegal. The scientific community is no exception to this new disease of plagiarism (copy – past) became prevalent in the era of new technologies and the Internet. Plagiarism affects all disciplines, sciences, humanities and medicine, written as figures. The situation becomes even more serious when, supposedly anonymous editors of journals, closing their eyes on plagiarism to "fill" the pages of journals and make a few dollars. Thus, none reviewed online publication would become common merchandise. In these disastrous practices, add the shameful "looting" of others works, practices that engage without remorse. We must fight against plagiarism today that the development of digital technologies not only tends to make it easier, but to trivialize it and thus make it almost normal. We have plenty of examples showing that plagiarism is increasingly commonplace in the word. Whereas matching an integral article (Copy and paste) from another scientific journal is a potential plagiarism qualified unjustified attitude and a stupid practice.

The most striking case, is the copy and paste of our article published since 2012 in this journal (PhytoChem & BioSub Journal Vol. 6 N° 2, 83-87, 2012, <http://pcbsj.webs.com/pcbs-j-vol-6-2012>) by another “ scientists” - teaching in Tlemcen and Bechar universities, L. Ziane, H. A. Lazouni, A. Moussaoui, N. Hamidi - and published in Asian Journal of Natural & Applied Sciences, Vol. 2(1), 5-9, 2013 ([www. leena-luna.co.jp](http://www.leena-luna.co.jp)). A journal with editorial board but the editor chief is anonymous.

A simple search of fragments of sentences of the article on Google quickly allowed us to see that this article is a gross plagiarism. The article (text, figure, and picture) is the integral copying of our works with slightly modification of title and introduction. As an anecdote, even the non-specialist reader can easily notice the stupidity of the authors of flight that indicated below:

Page 5: Introduction:

“ *The aim of this studies is to evaluate the bioactives extracts of *Limoniastrum feei* plant of the Southeast of Algeria (saoura region of Bechar) northern Africa [1-2] by phytochemical screening. In earlier work we have reported the antimicrobial activity of aerial part crude*

extracts from *Limoniastrum feei* (**Belboukhari et al 2005**). **In continuation of our studies on medicinal plants, we isolate two flavonoids from methanolic extract of *Limoniastrum feei*. [3-4]** “

Page 7: Ethno pharmacology Screening

“According to the results of ethno pharmacology study to several medical plants that are used in Bechar (Southeast of Algeria) in traditional medicine, **it carries out by laboratory LPSO (1998)**. We are interested to deepen the investigation of this specie.”

Page 8: Phytochemical Screening

“According to the results of biological screening of several extracts of three parts of *Limoniastrum feei* (leaves, stem and twig) [3- 4].The methanolic and heptan extracts of these parts of *Limoniastrum feei* were selected (table1) and were carried out a phytochemical screening on the active extracts for this plants.”

Page 9: References

On the 10 references cited, 6 are our publications!!!!

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I think this practice can not be ignored. It is a case of plagiarism rather disconcerting. But this example illustrates the potential dangers of the online diffusion of the article and the need for vigilance that editors of journal should keep. The academic and scientific communities must work together against all forms of plagiarism. They must do so not only in the prevention but also by adequate sanctions against proved plagiarism

Thus, any one, authors or publisher not condemn and promote these practices should be automatically disqualified from scientific research. The responsibility of editor against plagiarism must be engaged, at least by the retracted of article in question.

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